

DEVELOPING HIGHER ORDER THINKING SKILLS (HOTS) AMONG STUDENTS USING HOME-ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY WORKSHEETS (HESW) IN GRADE 9 ARALING PANLIPUNAN

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ABSTRACT

Economics as a science of choice involves a proficiency in Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS). Being able to choose wisely and correctly on how limited resources are to be utilized, necessitates both critical and creative thinking. Both of which depends on the activities that are given by the teacher to the students. The instructional resources made by teachers should offer opportunities for learners to broaden and strengthen their grasp of important economic concepts. This study attempted to determine the effects of using Home Engagement Strategy Worksheet (HESW) to HOTS of students. The research used descriptive method, specifically developmental in nature. Descriptive method is involved in describing the characteristics of the population such as their demographic profile like age and gender, and learner's attitude. Developmental in nature signifies that enhancement and conception of a particular material will be undertaken. To verify this, 110 grade 9 students at Quezon National High School in Lucena City for the School Year 2020-2021 were given the devised HESW. Then an achievement test was given to them. Mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentages, and Pearson product moment of correlation were the statistical treatment used in this study. The result of the achievement test showed excellent scores in both evaluating and analyzing while only fair score was achieved in creating. This means that the devised HESW was remarkably effective in developing evaluating and analyzing skills but failed to establish creating skills among students. The study suggests the need for devising home-engagement worksheets that will enhance not just the evaluating and analyzing skills of students but also their creating skills.

Keywords: Academic Guidance, Home Engagement, HOTS, Worksheets